

VIBRATIONAL AND DYNAMIC ANALYSIS OF A SMART NONSYMMETRICAL LAMINATED COMPOSITE BEAM

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ABSTRACT

An analytical model based on the Classical Laminate Plate Theory (CLPT) is presented to predict the vibrational and dynamic behavior of a smart orthotropic laminated composite cantilever beam subjected to transverse and axial loading. Considering von Karman theory, linear strain–displacement relations are determined. Then by assuming that the Kirchhoff hypothesis holds, the transverse displacement is considered to be independent of the transverse thickness coordinate, while the normal and transverse shear strains would be zero. By properly integrating the constitutive equations for each orthotropic and piezoelectric layer of the laminated smart beam, the relations between stress resultants and the deformation field is obtained without any further assumption on symmetry of the laminates. Then utilizing the dynamic version of the principle of virtual work, the equations of motion of the smart structure are derived. Assuming periodic solution for the field variables, the model provides predictions for all stress, strain and displacement components within each layer.

The predicted contour plots for field components are in acceptable correlation with the finite element method. Moreover, results for the natural frequencies of the smart beam show good agreement with other published analytical and finite element models. Results of this study revealed that the advantage of the presented model in comparison with the published finite element models is that the model can provide highly accurate closed-form results without assuming further simplifications. The model also has advantages over conventional analytical models for less simplifying assumptions of the symmetry of the laminate.

1 INTRODUCTION

Smart composite materials have wide, growing variety of usage in different applications including aerospace, automotive, military, construction, and medical industries [1]. A smart structure involves distributed actuators and sensors controlled by a main controller which analyses the responses from the sensors and engage the actuators to maintain the expected shape or to apply required force, strains or displacements to improve the whole structure's response [1]–[3]. Smart structures could be designed and manufactured with different arrangements [4], including insertion of the sensor between the plies[5], by cutting a host area in the composite plies[6], by locating them as dispersed or interlaced plies or utilizing monitoring patch technique [7].

In order to study behavior of different structural smart materials, several analytical models[5], [6], numerical techniques, and experimental works [6] have been developed. Different structural models including beams [8]–[10], thin/thick plates [8], [11], [12] and shells [13] are utilized in order to simulate behavior of smart composite and FGM structures under different types of actuation, loads and boundary conditions. For the most applicable numerical models, one can refer to finite element[8], [9], [13], differential quadrature methods [10], and meshless methods.

Various analytical macro-mechanical models have also been proposed to evaluate the behavior of smart structures. Among the first analytical approaches to model smart composite behavior is a closed-form solution for active vibration control of a flexible beam with SMA layers proposed by Chen and Levy[3]. They used the Euler–Bernoulli beam theory to model the SMA composite beam. Gharib et al. developed a closed form solution for bending of FGM beams integrated with piezoelectric layer [10].

Vel and Batra obtained an exact solution for cylindrical bending of laminated plates with embedded piezoelectric shear actuators [3].

In this paper, an analytical approach to study vibrational and transient dynamic response of laminated composite beams with integrated piezoelectric actuator is presented. Unlike most analytical models found in the literature which neglected or over-estimated the structural effect of the actuator layer, the presented model is capable of investigating non-symmetric orthotropic laminates. Furthermore, employing convolution integration, it could provide analytical solution for a range of different dynamic loadings without adding additional simplifying assumptions.

2 GOVERNING EQUATIONS

In order to describe the vibrational behavior of the smart material, we assume that the total strain in the transducer comprised of the mechanical strain applied by mechanical stress, and the strain generated by the applied voltage. In general, one can relate the strain and electric displacement to stress and electric field using equation (1), where $\epsilon_{xx}, \epsilon_{yy}, \epsilon_{zz}, \epsilon_{xy}, \epsilon_{xz}, \epsilon_{yz}$ are elements of the strain field, D_{xx}, D_{yy}, D_{zz} are elements of the electric displacement, $\sigma_{xx}, \sigma_{yy}, \sigma_{zz}, \sigma_{xy}, \sigma_{xz}, \sigma_{yz}$ are elements of the stress field, and E_{xx}, E_{yy}, E_{zz} are elements of the electric field. Furthermore, the terms $S_{11}, S_{12}, S_{13}, \dots, S_{66}$ are mechanical compliance elements, $d_{11}, d_{12}, d_{13}, \dots, d_{66}$ are electrical-mechanical interaction compliance elements, and $\zeta_{11}, \zeta_{12}, \zeta_{13}, \dots, \zeta_{66}$ are electrical compliance elements.

$$\begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_{xx} \\ \epsilon_{yy} \\ \epsilon_{zz} \\ \epsilon_{xy} \\ \epsilon_{xz} \\ \epsilon_{yz} \\ D_{xx} \\ D_{yy} \\ D_{zz} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} & S_{13} & S_{14} & S_{15} & S_{16} & d_{11} & d_{21} & d_{31} \\ S_{21} & S_{22} & S_{23} & S_{24} & S_{25} & S_{26} & d_{11} & d_{22} & d_{26} \\ S_{31} & S_{32} & S_{33} & S_{34} & S_{35} & S_{36} & d_{11} & d_{11} & d_{11} \\ S_{41} & S_{42} & S_{43} & S_{44} & S_{45} & S_{46} & d_{11} & d_{11} & d_{11} \\ S_{51} & S_{52} & S_{53} & S_{54} & S_{55} & S_{56} & d_{11} & d_{26} & d_{66} \\ S_{61} & S_{62} & S_{63} & S_{64} & S_{65} & S_{66} & d_{11} & d_{11} & d_{11} \\ d_{11} & d_{11} & d_{12} & d_{12} & d_{16} & d_{11} & \zeta_{11} & \zeta_{12} & \zeta_{13} \\ d_{11} & d_{11} & d_{21} & d_{22} & d_{26} & d_{12} & \zeta_{21} & \zeta_{22} & \zeta_{23} \\ d_{11} & d_{11} & d_{16} & d_{26} & d_{66} & d_{12} & \zeta_{31} & \zeta_{32} & \zeta_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{yy} \\ \sigma_{zz} \\ \sigma_{xy} \\ \sigma_{xz} \\ \sigma_{yz} \\ E_{xx} \\ E_{yy} \\ E_{zz} \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Assuming Classical Laminated Plate Theory where the Kirchhoff hypothesis holds, it is required that the displacement field $(\bar{u}, \bar{v}, \bar{w})$ to be such that [14] :

$$\begin{pmatrix} \bar{u}(x, y, z, t) \\ \bar{v}(x, y, z, t) \\ \bar{w}(x, y, z, t) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} u(x, y, t) \\ v(x, y, t) \\ w(x, y, t) \end{pmatrix} - z \begin{pmatrix} \partial w(x, y, t) / \partial x \\ \partial w(x, y, t) / \partial y \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Where u , v and w are displacement of mid-section points in the direction of beam length (x), width (y), and thickness (z) respectively (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: A typical composite beam composed of orthotropic layers integrated with piezoelectric actuator patch

The linear strain–displacement relations using the von Karman theory assumptions and displacement field (1) are found as follows:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx} \\ \varepsilon_{yy} \\ \varepsilon_{xy} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & 0 & -z \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \\ 0 & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & -z \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} \\ \left(\frac{1}{2}\right) \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & \left(\frac{1}{2}\right) \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & -z \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x \partial y} \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where $\varepsilon_{xx}, \varepsilon_{yy}, \varepsilon_{xy}$ are non-zero elements of the strain field. Accordingly, constitutive equations for each layer of the laminated smart beam could be written as:

$$\begin{pmatrix} N_{xx} \\ N_{yy} \\ N_{xy} \\ M_{xx} \\ M_{yy} \\ M_{xy} \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} N_{xx}^{(p)} \\ N_{yy}^{(p)} \\ 0 \\ M_{xx}^{(p)} \\ M_{yy}^{(p)} \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} & B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & A_{26} & B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} \\ A_{16} & A_{26} & A_{66} & B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} \\ B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} & D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{16} \\ B_{21} & B_{22} & B_{26} & D_{12} & D_{22} & D_{26} \\ B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} & D_{12} & D_{26} & D_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \partial u / \partial x \\ \partial v / \partial y \\ \partial u / \partial y + \partial v / \partial x \\ -\partial^2 w(x, y, t) / \partial x^2 \\ -\partial^2 w(x, y, t) / \partial y^2 \\ -\partial^2 w(x, y, t) / \partial x \partial y \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

In order to find the equations of motion of the smart laminated beam, the Hamilton principle is used to derive equations of motion for smart laminated beam. According to this principle, an equilibrium position in the structures holds if the following equality happens[10], where $\delta U_e, \delta U_s, \delta V$ and δK represent the virtual strain energy, virtual charge energy, work done by the applied mechanical loads and electrical voltages, and virtual kinetic energy of the system respectively.

$$\int_0^t (\delta U_e + \delta U_s + \delta V - \delta K) dt = 0 \quad (5)$$

Employing Euler-Lagrange method, we could find equations of motion of the system as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial N_{xx}}{\partial x} &= I_0 \frac{\partial^2 u_m}{\partial t^2} - I_1 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \left(\frac{\partial W_m}{\partial x} \right) \\ \frac{\partial^2 M_x}{\partial x^2} + q &= I_0 \frac{\partial^2 W_m}{\partial t^2} + I_1 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \left(\frac{\partial u_m}{\partial x} \right) - I_2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 W_m}{\partial x^2} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

To find natural frequency and mode shapes of the beam, we assume that the lateral and axial displacement could be assumed as a multiplication of space and time functions:

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, t) &= U(x) * \sin(\omega t) \\ w(x, t) &= W(x) * \sin(\omega t) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Applying equations of motion, we could find the 6th order equation describes the lateral displacement. (equation 8)

$$p_1 \frac{d^6 W}{dx^6} + p_2 \frac{d^4 W}{dx^4} + p_3 \frac{d^2 W}{dx^2} + p_4 W = 0 \quad (8)$$

In which p_1, p_2, p_3 and p_4 are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned}
p_1 &= F_{12}^2 - F_{11}F_{22} \\
p_2 &= (-I_0F_{22} + 2I_1F_{12} - I_2F_{11})\omega^2 \\
p_3 &= -(I_1^2 + I_0I_2)\omega^4 + I_0F_{11}\omega^2 \\
p_4 &= I_0^2\omega^4
\end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

where F_{11} , F_{12} , F_{22} are the axial, axial-flexural, and flexural terms of the compliance matrix accordingly. The above 6th order polynomial equation generally has roots in the form of: $r_1 = \pm\beta_1$, $r_2 = \pm\beta_2i$, $r_3 = \pm\beta_3i$. So the lateral and longitudinal space part of the displacement of the beam could be written as:

$$\begin{aligned}
W &= W_1 \sinh(\beta_1 x) + W_2 \cosh(\beta_1 x) + W_3 \sin(\beta_2 x) + W_4 \cos(\beta_2 x) \\
&\quad + W_5 \sin(\beta_3 x) + W_6 \cos(\beta_3 x) \\
U &= U_1 \sinh(\beta_1 x) + U_2 \cosh(\beta_1 x) + U_3 \sin(\beta_2 x) + U_4 \cos(\beta_2 x) \\
&\quad + U_5 \sin(\beta_3 x) + U_6 \cos(\beta_3 x)
\end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

Where U_1 to U_6 could be found as:

$$\begin{aligned}
U_1 &= W_2(z_1\beta_1^5 + z_2\beta_1^3 + z_3\beta_1) \\
U_2 &= W_1(z_1\beta_1^5 + z_2\beta_1^3 + z_3\beta_1) \\
U_3 &= W_4(-z_1\beta_2^5 + z_2\beta_2^3 - z_3\beta_2) \\
U_4 &= W_3(z_1\beta_2^5 - z_2\beta_2^3 + z_3\beta_2) \\
U_5 &= W_6(-z_1\beta_3^5 + z_2\beta_3^3 - z_3\beta_3) \\
U_6 &= W_5(z_1\beta_3^5 - z_2\beta_3^3 + z_3\beta_3) \\
z_0 &= (F_{12}I_0^2 - F_{11}I_1^2)\omega^4 \\
z_1 &= (F_{22}F_{11}^2 - F_{11}F_{12}^2)/z_0 \\
z_2 &= (F_{11}^2I_2 - 2F_{11}F_{12}I_1 + F_{12}^2I_0)\omega^2/z_0 \\
z_3 &= ((F_{12}I_0I_1 - F_{11}I_1^2)\omega^4 - F_{11}^2I_0\omega^2)/z_0
\end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to inspect the accuracy of the presented method, natural frequencies of boron-epoxy laminated beam with clamped-free boundary conditions are compared with those available in the literature.

First, linear natural frequencies of different symmetrical laminated cantilever beam obtained from the present method are compared with those reported by Reddy [14] and the results from finite element analysis carried out using ANSYS. The material properties as well as the dimensions of the laminated beam are listed in Table 1.

E_1 (msi)	E_2 (msi)	G_{12} (msi)	G_{13} (msi)	G_{23} (msi)	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}	ρ (Kg.m ⁻³)	L (mm)	Thick. (mm)
30	3	1.5	1.5	0.6	0.27	0.27	0.4	2320	1000	1

Table 1: Mechanical properties of boron-epoxy laminae

The lowest five natural frequencies obtained from the presented solution and exact solution for a clamped symmetrical laminated beam are compared in Table 2, which indicates that the results of the presented theory are in acceptable correlation with both published analytical, and finite element analysis. However, it should be mentioned that the classical shear deformation theory is used in the presented solution, while first order shear deformation theory is utilized by ANSYS which results in less than 0.5% differences in results.

Fundamental Natural Frequency (Hz)					
Laminate Configuration	Mode Shape	Reddy [14]	ANSYS (This work)	Analytical (This work) I2=0	Analytical (This work) I2≠0
[0/90] _s	1st	5.756	5.757	5.756	5.756
	2nd	36.074	36.056	36.074	36.073
	3rd	101.008	100.870	101.008	101.003
	4th	197.935	197.440	197.936	197.917
	5th	327.202	325.900	327.202	327.151
[0/90/0] _s	1st	8.029	8.028	8.029	8.029
	2nd	50.315	50.261	50.312	50.315
	3rd	140.882	140.530	140.866	140.882
	4th	276.073	274.830	276.013	276.073
	5th	456.368	453.140	456.212	456.368
[0 ₃ /90] _s	1st	12.121	12.117	12.120	12.121
	2nd	75.958	75.731	75.952	75.958
	3rd	212.685	211.150	212.641	212.685
	4th	416.778	411.270	416.619	416.778
	5th	688.964	674.620	688.545	688.965
[0/90 ₃] _s	1st	9.631	9.627	9.631	9.631
	2nd	60.354	60.199	60.349	60.354
	3rd	168.994	167.980	168.959	168.994
	4th	331.161	327.530	331.035	331.161
	5th	547.433	538.000	547.100	547.433

Table 2: Comparing different methods to find natural frequencies of several symmetric configuration of Boron-Epoxy cantilever beam laminates.

After validating the formulated model, to calculate the performance of the method for non-symmetrical general configuration, the first five natural frequencies for different arrangement of boron-epoxy laminated cantilever beam are compared to the finite element analysis results carried out using ANSYS, which is presented in table 3. Results of the comparison shows very good agreement between the presented analytical results and finite element output. It shows that the model is capable of predicting the natural frequencies without anymore requirement of numerical domain approximation.

Fundamental Natural Frequency (Hz)						
Laminate Configuration	Method	1st Mode	2nd Mode	3rd Mode	4th Mode	5th Mode
[0/90]	Analytical	1.598	10.015	28.043	54.951	90.837
	ANSYS	1.598	10.018	28.061	55.022	91.030
[0 ₂ /90]	Analytical	2.881	18.056	50.556	99.067	163.759
	ANSYS	2.882	18.061	50.582	99.162	164.020
[0 ₃ /90]	Analytical	4.304	26.973	75.523	147.987	244.617
	ANSYS	4.305	26.975	75.532	148.020	244.720
[0/90 ₃]	Analytical	2.933	18.382	51.466	100.845	166.686
	ANSYS	2.934	18.384	51.479	100.890	166.820

Table 3. natural frequencies of several non-symmetrical configuration of boron-epoxy cantilever beam laminates

Furthermore, in order to analyse the longitudinal and transverse behaviour of the non-symmetrical smart laminated cantilever beam integrated with piezoelectric actuator, the first five mode shapes of the [0/90] boron-epoxy cantilever beam integrated with the MFC-P1 piezoelectric actuator are presented in Fig. (2) and Fig. (3). The properties for the MFC-P1 piezoelectric actuator is as following:

E_1 (msi)	E_2 (msi)	G_{12} (msi)	ν_{12}	ν_{21}	ρ (Kg.m ⁻³)	Thick. (mm)	d_{33} (pF/cm ²)	d_{31} (pF/cm ²)
4.4	2.3	0.8	0.31	0.16	5440	0.3	400	1700

Table 4: Material properties of the MFC-P1 piezoelectric actuator

Results show the longitudinal/transverse displacement interaction in non-symmetrical smart laminates which considerably affects the vertical and horizontal deformation due to either axial, transverse or moment loads.

Figure 2: Lateral displacement mode shapes for a Clamped-Free [0/90] boron-epoxy laminate integrated with the MFC-P1 piezoelectric actuator

Figure 3: Longitudinal displacement mode shapes for a Clamped-Free [0/90] boron-epoxy laminate integrated with the MFC-P1 piezoelectric actuator

4 CONCLUSION

In this study, an analytical procedure is presented to investigate the vibrational and dynamic behavior of beams with different laminates configuration made of orthotropic materials to evaluate the accuracy and applicability of the proposed analytical method. To validate the results in both space and time domain, published data for the natural frequencies of laminated beam, as well as results of the new analysis carried out in ANSYS software is provided. Results revealed that the presented model has several advantages to precisely predict natural frequency, and mode shapes of non-symmetrical smart composite laminates without any further numerical simplifying assumptions. It should be mentioned that just considering the first few terms of the closed-form results for the smart beam can provide precise prediction of the behavior of the structure.

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